

A Radical Aesthetic Born out of Disillusionment : A Critical Study of the Aesthetics of the Hungry Generation

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Abstract

This paper deals with the Hungry Generation Movement which was one of the significant avant-garde movements in the history of Bengali literature. The first phase of this movement that spanned nearly four years from 1961 to 1965, took the Bengali literary scene by storm. This highly experimental movement included within its fold writers like Malay Roychoudhury and his brother Samir Roychoudhury, Shakti Chattopadhyay, Haradhan Dhara or Debi Roy, Subimal Basak, Subhash Ghosh, Shaileshwar Ghosh, Basudeb Dasgupta among others and two painters from Benaras, Anil Karanjai and Karunanidhan Mukhopadhyay. The movement took place in an era of disillusionment as the hope of an equal, progressive and liberal nation promised by the independence of India was shattered by the trauma of Partition, two unsatisfactory Five Years Plans of 1950s, corruption etc. Most of the Hungryalist writers came from outside Calcutta, the political and cultural capital of West Bengal, and through their writings relentlessly attacked the Bengali bourgeoisie whom they considered as the enemy of people's freedom. However, there is a dominant tendency to interpret the Hungryalist discourse by aligning it with the American Beat discourse which, in turn, makes the Hungryalist discourse appear derivative as well as inauthentic. Going against this trend, this paper attempts to undertake a contextual study of the movement to evince how the ideas and events of the zeitgeist left an indelible mark on their writings. In order to illustrate my points, I will attempt a critical reading of some of the short stories written by Subhash Ghosh to show the rootedness of their works.

Keywords: *Hungry Generation, avant-garde, post-independence disillusionment, enemy of freedom.*

The Hungry Generation movement was one of the significant avant-garde movements that took the Bengali literary world by storm. The most

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prominent phase of this anti-establishmentarian movement spanned nearly four years from 1961 to 1965 and included within its fold writers like Malay Roychoudhury, Subimal Basak, Haradhon Dhara or Debi Roy, Shakti Chattopadhyay, Utpal Kumar Basu, Shaileshwar Ghosh, Subhash Ghosh, Basudeb Dasgupta, Pradip Choudhury and two painters, Anil Karanjai and Karunanidhan Mukhopadhyay. This cohort of writers and artists known as the Hungryalists adopted a confrontational attitude towards the mainstream Bengali society and its culture. This movement attracted widespread public attention including the interests of international writers when many among the members were picked up and harassed by the police on charges of obscenity. The movement somewhat lost its steam when one of the leading members, Malay Roychoudhury, was sentenced to prison. Opinions regarding the Hungry Generation movement are extremely polarized with a large section of writers and critics being dismissive of the Hungryalists and particularly critical of their gender politics as opposed to some who praise them for their iconoclastic stance.¹ Without intending to add another brick to the ongoing controversies regarding the Hungry Generation, this essay sets out with a different set of objectives. It seeks to situate the Hungry Generation movement in the context of the post-independence West Bengal. It also aims to explore the modernist aesthetic developed by the Hungryalists which is often glossed over in the discussion of the larger narrative of the Bengali literary modernism.

Modernism, an aesthetic movement taking place in the early twentieth century, was never homogeneous or unitary. It was rather characterised by,

. . . a series of seeming contradictions: both a rejection of the past and a fetishization of certain earlier periods, both primitivism and a defence of civilization against the barbarians; both enthusiasm for the technological and fear of it; both a celebration of impersonal making and a stress on subjectivity.²

So, modernism can be perceived as a large cauldron into which different ideologies were thrown pell-mell. One of the reasons behind the continuous marginalization of the Hungryalist aesthetic is the tendency to read Bengali literary modernism with the help of a single narrative. In his introduction to the anthology titled *Adhunik bangla kabita* (1954), Buddhadeva Bose draws our attention to the variegated nature of the

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Bengali modernist poetry which can never be grasped with the help of a single marker :

... this modernist poetry is not something that can be unmistakably identified by a single sign. It can be called a poetry of rebellion and protest, of doubt, of boredom, of quest; again in it the awakening of wonder, the happiness of life, a mind faithfully inclined towards universal laws have been expressed.³

So, the discourse of the Hungry Generation needs to be viewed as one among the many other discourses in the heterogeneous field of Bengali literary modernism.

In order to analyze the works of the Hungryalists, it is imperative to understand the reality of the post-independence Indian nation-state out of which their writings emerged. The metropolis of Calcutta, which was the playing field of many of the Hungryalist writers, was in tatters at that time due to the dismemberment of Bengal into two provinces following the Independence of India in 1947. The constant influx of the refugees from East Pakistan coupled with the migration of people from the rural regions to the metropolis of Calcutta altered the demography of the metropolis altogether. The Partition and the concomitant swelling of population cast an adverse shadow on the economy of the state of West Bengal as well. The economy of the western province of the undivided Bengal was largely sustained by its industries, particularly by the jute, tea and paper industries. The essential raw materials for many of these industries were supplied by the agrarian eastern province which also acted as a market for many of western Bengal's finished products. But the Partition disrupted the supply of raw materials from eastern Bengal which, in turn, severely jeopardised the functioning of many of these large industries in West Bengal which were still running on older machineries and therefore were less productive. The central government was concerned about protecting the interests of industries which catered to the domestic market, but provided little help to the export-based industries. The fact that the major industries in West Bengal were mostly export-oriented did not help the state's cause. The post-independence economic immiseration in West Bengal caused by the decline in the industrial sector was further aggravated by a severe crisis in the agrarian sector. Observing the agrarian decline in West Bengal between the years 1951 and 1961, Joya Chatterji notes,

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In that decade, Bengal also lagged behind other Indian states in agriculture. It variously took twelfth, tenth, and ninth place in India for growth between 1952 and 1965 using the key agrarian measures of agricultural production, area under cultivation, and productivity gauged by yield per acre. By every one of these standards, West Bengal's agrarian growth had been far slower than the national average.⁴

The post-Independence agrarian decline not only affected the country's economy adversely but also created an acute food crisis in post-Partition West Bengal. The industrial western province of Bengal traditionally did not grow sufficient rice, the staple food of Bengal, for its people and therefore, had to rely on the agrarian eastern province for the supply of food grains, a system which broke down due to the Partition. After the Partition, the number of people in West Bengal increased exponentially due to the influx of the millions of refugees and huge rise in the birth rate, but the state authority already burdened with other concerns found it extremely difficult to provide food to so many people. The deepening food crisis led to periodic hunger marches in the state that culminated in the Food Movements of 1959 and 1966.

The rapid economic decline in West Bengal in the aftermath of the Partition created a set of problems for its inhabitants. In 1966, West Bengal was in the eighth position in the national league in the matter of per capita income, a significant decline from 1950 when the province's per capita income was highest in the country.⁵ The growth in population in an economically retarding state created a massive problem of white-collar unemployment, a problem that neither the public sector nor the private sector was able to address. Due to the combination of all these factors, West Bengal in the decades following the Independence became entrapped within the jaws of dire poverty. In 1962, the head count ratio of poverty in West Bengal was 62.2 percent as against 38.2 percent in India as a whole. By 1967-68, the corresponding all-India figure had risen to 55.8 percent, but in West Bengal it had reached an incredible 80.6 percent.⁶ The reigning Congress government of the state which was often accused by its detractors for preserving only the interests of the wealthy and the propertied, was inept to tackle the mounting economic crisis that threatened to corrode the bases of the post-Independence Bengali society. Calcutta was the first city

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in the Indian nation state where the problems of industrial recession, agrarian decline, population explosion, and unemployment were most starkly felt. This, in turn, signalled the death of the dreams offered by the Independence, particularly to the youth in West Bengal who became extremely sceptical toward the rhetoric of triumph and progress encircling the post-colonial nation state. Partha Chatterjee observes in this context,

Within ten years of Independence, when the dominant tone of political rhetoric in India was still that of enthusiasm for planning, industrial modernization and Nehruvian socialism, the voice of disenchantment was already beginning to be raised in the eastern metropolis.⁷

The Hungryalists appeared in the 1960s, a decade when the nation's escalating economic crisis appeared to many, as reaching its zenith. The resulting disillusionment with the society found its expression with all its severity in the writings of the Hungryalists most of whom were migrants to the city of Calcutta. The modernist movements throughout the world were spearheaded by writers and artists who were often immigrants to the metropolises. The metropolis with its cosmopolitan character provides a conducive environment for the writers and artists to create art. Pointing out the significance of metropolis in the modernist movement Raymond Williams observes,

Paris, Vienna, Berlin, London, New York took on a new silhouette as the eponymous City of Strangers, the most appropriate locale for art made by the restlessly mobile émigré or exile, the internationally anti-bourgeois artist. From Apollinaire and Joyce to Beckett and Ionesco, writers were continuously moving to Paris, Vienna and Berlin, meeting there exiles from the Revolution coming the other way, bringing with them the manifestos of post-revolutionary formation.⁸

We find James Joyce taking up residence in different metropolises like Trieste, Zurich and Paris, D. H. Lawrence coming to the metropolis of London from Nottinghamshire, T. S. Eliot and Ezra Pound coming to London from America, Arun Kolatkar and Arvind Krishna Mehrotra coming to the metropolis of Bombay from Kohlapur and Allahabad respectively. Malay and his brother Samir Roychoudhury and Subimal Basak came to the metropolis of Calcutta from Patna; Subhash Ghosh and

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Shaileshwar Ghosh came from Balurghat, Basudeb Dasgupta from Ashoknagar, Pradip Choudhury from Tripura, Anil Karanjai and Karunanidhan Mukhopadhyay from Benaras. Moreover, some of the members of this avant-garde movement like Shaileshwar Ghosh, Subhash Ghosh, Basudeb Dasgupta, Pradip Choudhury, Subo Acharya and Anil Karanjai were forced to cross over to the west from eastern Bengal due to the Partition. The Hungry Generation writers and artists forged their own distinctive modernist aesthetics which they fleshed out through their manifestoes. The use of the manifesto form, which was almost unprecedented in the field of Bengali art and literature, was perhaps indicative of their desire to state or create something new. They were particularly critical of their modernist predecessors and contemporaries who, they believed, could not delineate the present reality adequately in their writings.

In the first Bengali manifesto Malay Roychoudhury wrote, ‘Poetry is now poised at the opposite of life. It is no longer congruous with life. . . .’⁹ The separation of poetry from the praxis of life that Malay seemed to complain about, had started to a large extent with Buddhadeva Bose who championed the concept of ‘pure poetry’. Observing the Bengali literary scene of the late 1940s, Shankha Ghosh argued that the poets associated with Buddhadeva Bose’s *Kabita*, being inspired by the idea of ‘aesthetic exclusiveness’ cultivated ‘pure poetry’, ‘a kind of writing “that is good for all time, beautiful for all time, that can only be experienced by a pure soul in a peaceful setting.”’¹⁰ Although there was an alternative trend of socially committed literature endorsed by Bishnu Dey, Subhash Mukhopadhyay and others, as observed by Shankha Ghosh, that resisted decadence and detachment in literature,¹¹ it was the editor of *Kabita* whose approval was most earnestly sought by the majority of young poets of the 1950s. These poets being inspired by Buddhadeva’s creed of aesthetic autonomy started producing ‘neo-romantic’¹² texts that were delinked from the grim realities of post-Partition days. In a prose piece added at the end of the first issue of *Shatabhisha* (1951), Dipankar Dasgupta, one of the editors of the magazine, declared that they wanted to give priority to a poetry that, irrespective of its subject matter, would qualify aesthetically. In the introduction of his collection of poetry (1954), Jibananda Das, a modernist poet of the earlier generation, though not under the influence of Buddhadeva Bose,

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declared, ‘Poetry is the matter of aesthetics. . . .’¹³ The creed of art for art’s sake in the field of Bengali literature received further impetus when Buddhadeva Bose published his translation of the poetry of Charles Baudelaire in 1961. In the introduction of his translation, Bose argued that Baudelaire’s chief contribution lay in the ‘distillation and cultivation of romanticism.’¹⁴ This ‘distillation’ of romanticism or the elimination of the non-poetic from the poetic was attained by Baudelaire, Bose argued, by isolating the poet from the purview of society.¹⁵ *Krittibas* (1953) which presented itself as the ‘mouthpiece of the youngest poets’ absorbed some of the ideas of Buddhadeva whose influence on some of the early writings published in *Krittibas* was unmistakable.

Appearing in the 1960s, the Hungryalists through their writings repeatedly attacked the notion of an autonomous art and sought to tether art to the realities of life. In the first manifesto Malay declared, ‘To declare war against art is the first condition for the creation of poetry.’¹⁶ Shaileshwar Ghosh in his book *Hungry generation aandolon* wrote, ‘We thought about destroying the so-called “art” by the direct presentation of experiences.’¹⁷ In his poem ‘Rokto, tram er chakae’, Shaileshwar wrote, ‘The Kabita Bhaban made of plastic has lain being powdered at the effect of my strike.’¹⁸ Kabita Bhaban was the name of Buddhadeva Bose’s home at 202 Rashbehari Avenue and many of the works published by Bose carried the name of Kabita Bhaban as the publishing house. Shaileshwar presented his poetry as a direct challenge to the ‘pure’, self-contained poetry of Buddhadeva and his followers. Although some of the Hungry Generation poets including Malay Roychoudhury wrote in *Krittibas*, Malay’s first collection of poetry, *Shoetaner much* (1963) being published by *Krittibas*, there was a conscious attempt in the Hungryalists to oppose the *Krittibas* writers. In his essay ‘Krittibas theke hungry andolon: bangla kabitar palabodol’ (2003), Malay charted out the differences between the Hungryalists and the *Krittibas* group. One of the major differences as pointed out by Malay was that whereas the discourse of *Krittibas* was influenced by the ‘colonial’ notion of art for art’s sake, the ‘counter discourse’ of the Hungry Generation was constructed to challenge different institutions of society.¹⁹ According to Malay, whereas *Krittibas* was a centralized group, no one being allowed to write there without the approval of the editor, and its prominent members belonged to the upper caste, the

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majority of Hungry Generation writers and artists who were not under any kind of central leadership, came from the lower echelons of the social hierarchy.²⁰ However, it cannot be denied that many of the *Krittibas* writers did indeed partake in the radical environment of the 1960s, and as a consequence the works of writers like Shakti Chattopadhyay, Sunil Gangopadhyay and Sarat Kumar Mukhopadhyay of that phase were marked by the presence of radical and subversive elements. But when Sunil forged a link between poetry and consumption by composing lines such as ‘I have written poems, now I want scotch, white horse, cooked in pure ghee/ Chicken legs. . . .’²¹ or when he along with Shakti and a large number of other *Krittibas* writers joined *Anandabazar*, one of the ‘institutions’ in the field of Bengali literature, it substantially undermined the anti-establishmentarian stance of *Krittibas*.

In order to depict the reality of post-independence West Bengal, the Hungryalist writers did not take recourse to the realist mode which they considered inadequate for accomplishing their purpose. As the Aristotelian notion of mimesis is central to the idea of realism, one of the objectives of the Hungryalist writing as laid out by Malay Roychoudhury, was not to imitate Aristotle’s realism.²² Their rejection of the realist mode also aligned them with other modernists and postmodernists. As Malcolm Bradbury writes in his essay ‘Modernisms/Postmodernisms’,

What Modernism and postmodernism share in common is a single adversary which is, to put it crudely, realism or naive mimesis. Both are forms of post-Realism. They likewise share in common a practice based on avant-garde and movement tactics and a sense of modern culture as a field of anxious stylistic formation.²³

The Hungryalist writers and artists sought to explore the reality of the unconscious. Shaileshwar wrote, ‘We want to use language to awaken the dormant layer of consciousness- in the task of establishing a link with the unconscious.’²⁴ Subhash Ghosh and Basudeb Dasgupta attempted to portray through their writings a deeper reality existing beneath the reality of the surface. In their writings we often find the real and the unreal, the conscious and the unconscious move into one another. This tendency to explore the realm of the unconscious for ‘higher truths’²⁵ brought their writings closer to surrealism, a twentieth century art movement that under the influence of the ideas of Sigmund Freud, was concerned with the

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portrayal of the reality of the unconscious. The influence of surrealism came over a number of Bengali writers of the 1960s largely through the works of Jibanananda Das and the American Beats. The Hungryalists like the Surrealists also emphasized on spontaneous writing that can be produced, they believed, through an unobstructed articulation of unconscious elements. In the first manifesto, Malay wrote,

The period of making poetry by lighting the table-lamp and the cigarette, and by dipping the pen into cerebral cortex has ended. Now poetry is composed in orgasm like spontaneity.²⁶

Like the surrealists, the Hungryalists also refrained from reshaping their writings which, they believed, would destroy the spontaneous nature of their writings. This reluctance to refine their works, which becomes evident when one looks at their manuscripts, however, marked them different from many of their preceding modernists like Sudhindranath Dutta who had the predilection to refine his works continuously to make them as perfect as possible. In the manifesto on short story, the Hungryalists defined the short story as a kind of ‘anti-descriptive subtle injury’ whose task is not the communication of incidents or ideas.²⁷ The Hungryalist short story writers, therefore, discarded the notion of a well-developed logical plot. They rather conceived the short story as the ‘crystal’ of the ‘anarchy’ of ‘today’s fragile life.’²⁸ The Hungryalists, all of them in their twenties during the heydays of the movement, found themselves in a post-Partitioned disillusioned milieu that instilled a sense of fear and anxiety in them. If we critically analyze some of the short stories of Subhash Ghosh and Basudeb Dasgupta, we will find the protagonists frequently grappling with a sense of fear and anxiety. One of the prominent sources of fear in the 1960s West Bengal for the youth was the interventionist nation state and the police as a repressive apparatus of the state. After the India-China border war of 1962, any kind of dissent was brutally suppressed throughout the nation. The crackdown on the Hungryalists in 1964 for their writing of ‘obscene’ texts, therefore, can be seen as a part of the nationwide programme of muzzling the dissent. The fear of the repressive state and its police among the youth repeatedly came up as a subject in the writings of the Hungryalists that sought to explore the psychic reality of the protagonists.

In Subhash Ghosh’s story ‘Khalasitolar 3no.’,²⁹ the narrator seemed to

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reside in a police state where any infringement of the law was treated with severe punishment. The narrator as he was chasing the dices of pasha was shackled after being halted by the red light of the traffic. But he subverted the law through his act of climbing the signal post after breaking the shackle and his attempt to break the red light, a controlling mechanism of the state. Therefore, in order to discipline the law-breaking narrator, the police as a repressive mechanism of the state appeared. The narrator was initially able to see only a pair of heavy boots approaching towards the post. It suggests that the policeman appeared to the narrator only as a dehumanized figure in service of the state. The bandaged forehead, red face and black dress of the policeman projected him as an agent of death. The sharp white nails and the skull that he showed the narrator further strengthen the association between death and the police. The flying saucer that rescued the narrator can be seen as an embodiment of his desire to move out of the situation in which he found himself being trapped. His act of vomiting and his removal of his own dresses perhaps suggest his desire to shun from his existence all the vestiges of human civilization. The shackled hands behind the bars that the narrator perceived perhaps indicate that the state has become a prison house in which individuals often find themselves in a state of incarceration. However, the flying saucer also failed to rescue him as he was suddenly invaded by a large number of vultures who started biting his body parts. The ferocious vultures can be seen as the coercive agents of the state. Eventually he fell from the saucer into the bloody mouth of the vultures being pulled down by a sharp wire. It perhaps denotes that in the post-independence India of the 1960s, it was almost impossible for a person to liberate himself or herself from the iron grip of the repressive state.

Basudeb Dasgupta's 'Randhansala'³⁰ is set in the context of the escalating food crisis in post-Partition West Bengal. We find the narrator who can be seen as an embodiment of the human unconscious, residing in a primitive place surrounded by forest, river and desert being completely delinked from human society and surviving on the algae which had grown on the walls of his ice-made room. His friend, Robin, whom he discovered at the bank of the river with a number of scars on his body, can be seen as the other half of his self that was more attuned to human society. It perhaps explains Robin's desire to return to the reality of the human society in spite

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of acknowledging that he had been beaten and thrown into the river by 'them'. The unknown bird whose human-like cries frightened them can be seen as an embodiment of the pain, misery and helplessness of the human society. Realizing the absence of the ingredients required to cook the lamb that the narrator had killed, they together set sail on the river to go to the other side for bringing the necessary ingredients. The river can be seen as the threshold between the reality of the human society and the unreal world of the unconscious. The harsh and oppressive nature of the human world became evident when they were subjected to merciless physical torture at the suggestion of an old man by the people waiting for them there. When they started cooking the lamb, they found their room beginning to melt down. It suggests that the unreal world in which the narrator and Robin lived, began to crumble down the moment they became engaged in cooking, an act that could link them to the human world. The bird reappeared and let out a cry that resembled the cry of a newly born parentless child for a drop of milk. The cry of the bird dissuaded them from eating the roasted lamb as Robin said, 'We at least have been able to spend our life eating algae, but for our children and grandchildren, even that much is not left.'³¹ So, they refrained from eating the meat thinking about the succeeding generations who would be the victims of the same food crisis. At the end, they together started eating voraciously the entrails, horn and skin of the lamb. It shows the failure of Robin or the civilized part of his self to bring the narrator back to the reality of the human world. It was rather the narrator who succeeded in drawing Robin from the frightening reality of the human society into the 'primitive' world of the unconscious.

The stories analyzed above repeatedly blurred the boundary between the real and the unreal, the conscious and the unconscious. As a consequence, the readers remain uncertain whether the incidents took place in the real world or they were the external projections of the protagonists' unconscious fears and desires. This non-realist narrative mode enabled the Hungryalists to portray a deeper reality which, in turn, would facilitate the readers, as they hoped, to have a better understanding of the reality of post-Independence West Bengal.

One of the recurring ideas in the poetics of the Hungry Generation was the self-exploration and self-revelation of the poet. In his essay 'Amar generation er kabyadarshan', Malay wrote,

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“What am I? Who am I? Why am I? How am I? Where am I?”-
Poetry has nothing more to do apart from the injury and explosion
of all these questions. Poetry results from the extreme unimpeded
attempt to see the inner realm of existence by ripping apart all its
awkwardness.³²

According to Malay, one of the major objectives of Hungryalist writing is the ‘barbaric discovery of the complete selfhood of the subject.’³³ Shaileshwar Ghosh echoed Malay’s view when he said, ‘My consciousness is my subject.’³⁴ Though the Hungryalists derived the template of self-centric writing from *Krittibas* and from the American Beats, they also altered it to make it much more political. According to the Hungryalists, the poet in the course of writing is in a state of becoming or in a state of self-discovery which can be attained through a revaluation of the existing societal values. This revaluation of values was inextricably tied in their poetics to the search of a new language. The Hungryalists’ search for a new idiom can be better understood if seen in the larger context of Bengali literary modernism.

In a prose piece added at the end of *Damayanti* (1943), Buddhadeva Bose projected as his aim *baakchandyer songe kabyachandyer milon* (‘the unification of the verbal rhythm with the rhythm of poetry’) and in order to accomplish this, set out for himself certain rules such as adherence to the verbal style of sentence construction, complete renunciation of verb forms in sadhu bhasha and poetic words etc.³⁵ Therefore, it appears extremely contradictory when he advocates, at the same time, the use of rhythm, rhyme and a grave and Sanskritized language in poetry as these components tend to cordon off poetry from the everyday human speech. His upholding of a *sugambhir-sanskritic* (‘grave-Sanskritized’) language of poetry was based on his belief that *drirota* (‘firmness’) and *sanhati* (‘coherence’) in poetic composition can be attained through a wide use of Sanskrit words.³⁶ The views of Sudhindranath Dutta is also extreme germane to our understanding of the Bengali modernists’ use of language. In ‘Kabyer mukti’, Sudhindranath recommended an adherence to the words of dictionary in the composition of poetry:

If the objective of poetry is to build a bridge of compassion between
the writer and the reader, the words of poetry then must need to take
shelter in any of the corners of dictionary. By this logic I am not

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trying to deprive the poet of his/her perennial right of creating new words, but just stating that mature words are more industrious than suckling words.³⁷

However, the ‘Sanskritized’ language of Buddhadeva or the ‘mature words’ of Sudhindranath was considered unsuited by the Hungryalists for the delineation of their lived reality. As Shaileshwar Ghosh wrote in ‘Kobitar biruddhye bidroho (i)’,

The attack was of that disease whose name is life. The language to express life was not being found, that the prevalent language, words would be of no use, was realized far ago and therefore, it could not be started in that way.³⁸

In order to accomplish their aim of bringing poetry closer to ‘life’, the Hungryalists sought to incorporate into their writings words that, they believed, were used by people inhabiting the lower echelons of the social hierarchy. In his poem ‘Jakham’³⁹ Malay wrote,

*Akhchar jong dhore jachey bohubyabohrito mangsopeshite
Matir songe 1 joge gole ghyat hoe jachey gyani ar murkher
samasya mora
Gorbher fyachange
I ta kore conversion chart nie oth pete royeche protiti nari.⁴⁰*

Words like *akhchar*, *ghyat*, *fyachang* were not much used in the field of the Bengali modernist writing and were certainly far removed from the Sanskritized language and ‘mature words’ upheld by Buddhadeva and Sudhindranath respectively. Subimal Basak wrote *Chhatamatha*, a novella, and *Habijabi*, a collection of poetry, entirely in the Kutti dialect which is used largely by a certain section of the lower class people in Dhaka. In ‘Habijabi 8’,⁴¹ Subimal Basak wrote,

*Ahom ami ki jyan korum, thiksir bujhte partachi na
Ei prithimmite ami ekerre huda haate aichi, ho, kotha manen
Michiler bhitre amare hajir haoner laigya dak parchilo
Karu loge ami gola milaite pari nai.⁴²*

In order to undermine the ‘elitist’ language of their predecessors, the Hungryalists also loaded much of their writings with slangs and sexual references, which were deemed ‘obscene’ in the Bengali bourgeois society, thereby producing violent shock effects. In his controversial poem,

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‘Prochondyo boidyutik chutar’, Malay wrote,

Mother, why did not you give me birth in the form of a skeleton?

Then I would have kissed God’s ass for two billion light years

But nothing pleases me, I do not like anything

I feel nauseated with more than a single kiss

Forgetting woman at the time of rape, I have returned to art on many days⁴³

The Hungryalists’ use of dialect words, slangs, terms with sexual connotations can also be interpreted as an attempt to subvert the class and caste boundaries prevalent within the Bengali language. These invisible borderlines in order to preserve the supposed ‘purity’ of the linguistic field deny access to certain words and phrases. If we consider language as a carrier of meaning or a storehouse of experiences, the language of the bourgeoisie through its exclusion of certain words refuses to acknowledge the alternative experiences of people subservient to the bourgeoisie. Attacking the concept of a language stratified across the class and caste lines, Malay Roychoudhury wrote in his essay ‘Oshlilota’, ‘I will treat obscenity with indulgence as I will destroy the class divisions existing within language.’⁴⁴ It can be argued that as the Hungryalist writers were immigrants to the city, they did not feel any compulsion to conform to the linguistic standards set up by the urban Bengali bourgeoisie.

In his writings, Shaileshwar Ghosh frequently linked the idea of self-discovery through language with the liberation of the individual. The bourgeois society, according to Shaileshwar, suppresses the freedom of its people by utilizing language as an instrument. In a poem titled ‘Nijer songe prolap’, Shaileshwar Ghosh wrote, ‘Human speech, I suspect you.’⁴⁵ The ‘suspicion’ that Shaileshwar felt toward human speech can be attributed to the fact that language being an arbitrary medium can be manipulated by those in power in order to propagate their own values through it as ‘truths’. According to Shaileshwar Ghosh, as human beings are regulated by the language of power built on the values of the hegemonic centre, they are unable to articulate due to the absence of an adequate language certain experiences that appear ‘subversive’ to the authority. So, the Hungryalist writer was invested with the responsibility to create new values and significance of things by dismantling the values inscribed on them by the hegemonic authority:

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Breaking the conspiratorial position of things, only the poet can create the real position and significance of things (the names). And because of that the structure of reality created by power crumbles down.⁴⁶

In order to shatter the values created by language, Nietzsche's Zarathustra suggests the use of 'will to power' that leads one to the revaluation of things:

Only through evaluation is there value: and without evaluation the nut of existence would be hollow. Hear it, you creative men!

A change in values- that means a change in the creators of values.

He who has to be a creator always has to destroy. . . .⁴⁷

In Hungryalist poetry, we find the poetic self continuously places itself in relation to different things and/or events and reevaluates their significance thereby discarding the values imposed upon them by the Bengali bourgeoisie. One of the objectives of the Hungryalist poetry, according to Malay, was 'To challenge every value with one's own self and thereafter to accept or to reject'. This desire to reevaluate everything in relation to the self thereby establishing the sovereignty of the self over everything was, according to Malay, the 'hunger' of the Hungry Generation writers and artists.⁴⁸ The Hungryalist writer sought to create a chaos by discarding bourgeois values. It was one of the reasons behind his exploration of the unconscious which was seen by them as the repository of the ideas and values suppressed by the bourgeois society. So, by recovering those values, those 'higher truths', they attempted to challenge the bourgeois value system which, they believed, keep people in subjugation.

The Hungryalists' rejection of the bourgeois values needs to be in the larger political context of post-independence India. The heterogeneous groups of people involved in the struggle for independence from the British had different expectations about freedom. It was hoped by the participants in the freedom struggle that the Independence would be a panacea for all their problems which were never homogeneous. The failure of the much-anticipated Independence impelled the people to 'invent' different enemies of freedom who were intent upon blocking the fulfilment of their needs and desires. As Sekhar Bandyopadhyay writes,

Divergent visions of freedom led to different imaginings of the enemy and resulted in contested strategies of political mobilization to encounter

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them. And it was through these encounters that there emerged what some historians have described as a new hybrid modernity.⁴⁹

The people of the lower middle class did not have any control over the economic matters of the state as they did not form any alliance either with the Bengali middle class businessmen or with the Bengali service communities. The youth of this economically disadvantaged class identified the bourgeoisie backed by the Congress government as the real enemy of their freedom. Their violent opposition to the bourgeoisie reached its peak in the 1960s, a decade when the escalating economic crisis with all its repercussions was most acutely felt, a period that begot the radical aesthetics of the Hungryalists. Most of the Hungryalist writers hailed from the lower middle class background and they believed that liberation could only be gained by breaking the dominant bourgeois values. Their subversive acts of sending animal masks to the politicians with the caption 'Please put off your mask' or their giving of shoe-box and blank page to the reviewers of reputed newspapers and magazines can be seen as their attempt to directly confront the bourgeois establishment. Such confrontational attitude separated the Hungryalists from other literary groups such as *Krittibas*, *Shatabhisha*, *Shruti*, *Shastrabirodhi*, *Nim* etc.

In his poem 'Ghorar songe bhoutik kothabarta' Shaileshwar Ghosh wrote,

Impregnating three widows, I am lying on the holy bed
O horse, the drinking of three glasses of health-nectar in Calcutta
The priest's name printed cloth and Gita laugh without salvation
The law of dhatu rolls about seven times- three widows
Travel to the southern sea for airing
Thirty three gods enjoy the reward- the peasants give the taxes
The holy thief is at the front door- all the girls of the domestic household
Breaking their spinster sleep bolts the door throughout the night
Reading Puranas and Gita, they learn to preserve their family customs, O horse you
Give love to the cocoons, where is the heart!
Hearing the reading of Gita, semen gathers in the testicles of dogs
Horse you on the bodies of thirty three crore holiness
Write a list of names, where is the heart?
Impregnating three widows, I am lying without any holiness

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Under the mystery o horse

Traversable road have lain empty for a long distance.⁵⁰

The three widows can be interpreted as the three cardinal principles of life-*Satya* (Truth), *Shiva* (God), and *Sundar* (Beauty) which the poet has conquered. They are widows because their ‘husband’ God who used to control them is dead. Moreover, they are also compared with the three glasses of nectar of health that enable the poet for the composition of poetry. The poet states that thirty three gods enjoy the reward while the farmers pay the taxes. It suggests the severe exploitation of peasantry in post-Independence Bengal by the persons enjoying God-like power. The girls of the domestic household who are devoid of hearts appear to the poet as mere ‘cocoon’ and not as human beings. The poet savagely derides the efforts of the girls to preserve family customs by reading the Puranas and the Gita by claiming that the dogs become sexually charged hearing the reading of the Gita. The poet here presents a mordant critique of the bourgeois ideas of honour and chastity to which the girls attempt to conform. The poet claims that after impregnating the three widows, he lies without any sense of holiness. It denotes the poet’s transcendence of the traditional ideas of good and evil. The traversable empty road which can be interpreted as the road for his poetic journey, has opened up after his impregnation of the three widows. The poem also acquires an altogether different dimension if we consider that it is the first poem of *Jonmo niyontron*, Shaileshwar’s first collection of poetry. The Indian government’s policy of birth control which reached extremely shocking heights during the Emergency from 1975 to 1977 had already started to be implemented largely on the poor, illiterate masses in the 1960s. ‘Ghorar songe bhoutik kothabarta’ ends with a powerful image of impregnation. So, Shaileshwar Ghosh’s poem can be seen as a counter-narrative that presented a resistance to the official discourse of birth control.

In a poem titled ‘Terminus par hote giye’, Shaileshwar Ghosh wrote,

The jollyboat of civilization is empty today- the use of iron has increased

The opium-addicted drunkard has forgotten his own name, here

I will see the habitation of the dead-

I understood anus as mouth

I have known that the second name of vagina is life

I have known the toilet as the kitchen

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Only after defecation, relief comes to the heart
Oh, I want relief, I want peace
I want to remain far away from the surrounding noises
Take me away from the uses of copper and steel⁵¹

The ‘opium-addicted drunkard’ can be seen as the technophile human civilization which has forgotten its name- its identity. Therefore, instead of human life, the poet fears that he will see here ‘the habitation of the dead’. Both the anus and the vagina are integral parts of the human anatomy, but any reference to these body parts particularly in the sphere of culture is deemed ‘obscene’ in the bourgeois society and therefore is frowned upon. However, in the poet’s radical re-evaluation, vagina is identified as the source of life. As he feels caged in the bourgeois industrial society, he desperately longs for a pre-industrial life. After the Independence, industrial development was vigorously pursued in the regime of Nehru as part of the modernization of the country. In the poem ‘Terminus par hote giye’, the poet presents his dissent toward the Indian government’s drive for industrial development as he is much more concerned about the repercussions of industrial progress.

In Hungryalist writing, there is a tendency in the writer to assume the consciousness of the marginalised and the oppressed and to launch a critique from that position of the prevailing values of the bourgeois ruling elite in post-independence India. Shaileshwar wrote,

Man is creating moralities one after another, I am separated from this chain of history- I am downtrodden. The world will move on excluding me. Therefore, I will need to create another world. And definitely that will be a counter-world which will similarly be moving and active like this world.⁵²

However, this tendency to identify with the consciousness of the oppressed was mingled with their reverential attitude towards art, an attitude that closely aligned them with other modernist writers and artists. In the first Hungryalist manifesto, Malay Roychoudhry claimed, ‘Man, God, Democracy, and Science have been vanquished. Poetry is now the only shelter.’⁵³ The attribution of such importance to poetry divulges their affinity with certain ideas of nobility, a class which is diametrically opposite to the lower class. This enshrining of art can be looked upon as a response to bourgeois philistinism and mercantilism. However, there

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appears a contradiction in the writings of the avant-garde Hungryalists where the concept of art is repeatedly attacked. However, it can be said that the art toward which the Hungryalists explicitly articulated their disdain was a self-serving art backed by the literary and the cultural establishment. The Hungryalists on the other hand prioritized an art which was deeply rooted in society.

Situating the avant-garde writers and artists in the dissident bourgeoisie, Raymond Williams argued that the avant-garde combined the aristocratic critique of the bourgeoisie with the working class critique in their denunciation of the bourgeoisie, a tendency manifested in the writings as well as in the lifestyle of the Hungryalists. The bohemian way of life adopted by the Hungryalists can be perceived both as elitist as well as marked by a striving to identify with the lifestyle of the people inhabiting the lower rungs of the bourgeois society. This identification of the avant-garde with the working class is born out of their shared sense of oppression in the bourgeois society and therefore, according to Williams, is a 'negative identification'.⁵⁴ However, in his essay entitled 'Choritrohinotar proyojon', Shaileshwar Ghosh advocated the idea of a classless writer:

. . . one who is a genuine writer does not have any class, he is classless. Though he is born among the proletariats and is one of them, the moment he starts to write, he does not remain a proletariat anymore.⁵⁵

It somewhat echoes the views of Wyndham Lewis articulated in his Vorticist magazine, *Blast*:

The moment a man feels and realizes himself as an artist, he ceases to belong to any milieu or time. Blast is created for this timeless, fundamental Artist that exists in everybody.⁵⁶

So, there appears a contradiction in the Hungryalist discourse between the idea of a classless artist and the attempt to assume the consciousness of the suppressed in the writings, a problem that acquires further complexities due to the fact that the Hungryalist writings are confessional in nature. Shaileshwar Ghosh attempted to resolve this contradiction by claiming that the moment one begins a conscious self-exploration, he or she no longer remains a proletariat. However, it can also be viewed in this way that emancipating the artist from any class mooring will not only make his

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voice more universal but also enable him to make use of different discourses in his fight against the bourgeois value system. Shaileshwar Ghosh widened the definition of the proletariat by including within its fold people from different strata of the class hierarchy who are shackled by the bourgeois value system. So, the idea of an artist speaking to everyone who feels suppressed in the bourgeois society and putting up a resistance against the bourgeois ruling elite by combining the upper class and lower class critiques of the bourgeoisie fits well into the poetics of the Hungryalists.

The Hungryalists' attempt to bring a change in the social order closely aligned them with the other radical youths of the 1960s West Bengal. In his writings, Shaileshwar Ghosh often conceived the poet as a revolutionary. Rejecting the epithet of the 'rebellious poet', Shaileshwar Ghosh argued that the word, poet, itself has all the connotations of revolution.⁵⁷ The poet, according to Ghosh, is someone who refuses to accept the dangerous, conspiratorial position of things in life.⁵⁸ So, we can clearly perceive a shift from the notion of the socially non-committal Baudelairean poet upheld by Buddhadeva Bose and his followers to the idea of a revolutionary poet propagated by the Hungryalists. This is also a clear departure from Sudhindranath's impersonal poet whom Sudhindranath in his essay 'Kabyer mukti' compared to a matchmaker.⁵⁹ The Hungryalist poet sought to make the readers 'hostile' through his subversive writing so that they would be incited by the 'liberated' language of the poet to seek their own liberation.⁶⁰ So, the Hungryalist poet can be seen as the harbinger of change who considers his poetry as a 'violent and sabotaging creativity'.⁶¹

The Hungryalist writers and artists emerged at a period when the state of West Bengal entered in its 'painful adolescence'.⁶² The Partition inflicted a severe a damage on it from which it never quite recovered. The rapid socio-economic decline of the state, a direct offshoot of the Partition, dashed the hopes and dreams of the youth which, in turn, created a profound sense of disillusionment in them with the Indian nation state. Hailing from lower middle class background, the Hungryalists as outsiders to the city were able to grasp perhaps more adequately through their writings this post-independence disillusionment. When they appeared in the literary scene, the modernist tradition was in a crisis. Some of the major ideas of the modernist tradition proved untenable in the changing context of the post-independence Bengal. Therefore, there was a need to reinvent modernism.

The Hungryalists participated in this project and developed their own radical avant-garde aesthetics which enabled them to give expression to their zeitgeist.

Endnotes:

- ¹ For a feminist critique of the writings of the Hungryalists, see, Nandini Dhar, 'Reading Hungryalists as One Who Came After: A Feminist Critique', *Café Dissensus* 26 (2016) : n.p. Web. <https://cafedissensus.com/2016/06/16/reading-hungryalists-as-one-who-came-after-a-feminist-critique/>. Accessed 23rd September 2018. For a criticism of the Hungryalists from a Marxist perspective, see, Barunjoyti Chaudhury, *Adhunikota adhunikottorbaad uttor adhunikota tatty o proyog* (Kolkata: Ekush Satak, 2012), pp. 146-192. For a critical appreciation of the Hungryalist texts, see, Satya Guha, *Ekaler gadya padya andoloner dalil* (North 24 Parganas: Dhriti Publication, 1999), pp. 144-202.
- ² Tim Armstrong, *Modernism: A Cultural History* (Cambridge: Polity Press, 2005), p.5.
- ³ Buddhadeva Bose, ed., *Adhunik bangla kabita* (Calcutta : M. C. Sarkar and Sons Pvt. Ltd., 1954), p.8.
- ⁴ Joya Chatterji, *The Spoils of Partition: Bengal and India 1947-1967* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2007), pp. 238-239.
- ⁵ Joya Chatterji, *The Spoils*, p. 238.
- ⁶ A. K. Bagchi, 'Studies on the Economy of West Bengal since Independence', *Economic and Political Weekly* 33. 47/48 (Nov. 21 - Dec. 4, 1998): 2977.
- ⁷ Partha Chatterjee, 'The Political Culture of Calcutta,' in Sukanta Chaudhuri, ed. *Calcutta: The Living City. Volume II: The Present and the Future* (New Delhi: Oxford University Press, 1990), p. 30.
- ⁸ Raymond Williams, *The Politics of Modernism: Against the New Conformists* (London: Verso, 1989), p. 34.
- ⁹ Malay Roychoudhury, *Ishtahar sankalan* (Baruipur: Mahadiganta, 1985), p. 5.
- ¹⁰ Shankha Ghosh, "'Towards a New Beginning": The Literary World of Modern Calcutta, 1941-1980,' in Sukanta Chaudhuri, ed. *Calcutta: The Living City. Volume II: The Present and the Future* (New Delhi: Oxford University Press, 1990), p. 232.
- ¹¹ Shankha Ghosh, "'Towards a New Beginning,'" p. 233.
- ¹² For a detailed discussion of the emergence of the neo-romantic trend in the Bengali poetry of the 1950s, see Alokeranjan Dasgupta and Deviprasad

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Bandyopadhyay ed. *Aadhunik kavitar itihās* (Kolkata: Dey's Publishing, 2011), pp. 157-165.

- ¹³ Jibanananda Das, Introduction. *Jibanananda Daser srestho kabita* (Calcutta: Navana, 1954), n.p.
- ¹⁴ Buddhadeva Bose, Introduction. *Charles Baudelaire o tar kabita* (Calcutta: Dey's Publishing, 1961), p.5.
- ¹⁵ Buddhadeva Bose, *Charles Baudelaire*, p. 9.
- ¹⁶ Malay Roychoudhury, *Ishtahar*, p. 5.
- ¹⁷ Shaileshwar Ghosh, *Hungry generation aandolon* (Calcutta: Khudhartho prakashani, 1995), p. 39.
- ¹⁸ Shaileshwar Ghosh, *Shreshtho kabita* (Kolkata : Dey's Publishing, 2012), p. 33.
- ¹⁹ Malay Roychoudhury, 'Krittibas theke hungry aandolon: bangla kabitar palabodol,' in *Hungry kinbadanti-II* (Kolkata: Avishkar prakashani, 2013), p.106.
- ²⁰ Malay Roychoudhury, 'Krittibas theke hungry aandolon', pp. 104-106.
- ²¹ Shankha Ghosh, "Towards a New Beginning," p. 240.
- ²² Malay Roychoudhury, *Ishtahar*, p. 7.
- ²³ Sipra Mukherjee, *Modern English Literature, 1890-1960* (Hyderabad: Orient Black Swan, 2016), p. 210.
- ²⁴ Shaileshwar Ghosh, *Hungry generation aandolon*, p. 22.
- ²⁵ See, Malay Roychoudhury, 'Amar generation er kabyadarshan,' in *Hungry kinbadanti-II* (Kolkata: Avishkar prakashani, 2013), pp. 17-32. This idea of a 'higher truth' was reiterated in many of the works of the Hungryalists.
- ²⁶ Malay Roychoudhury, *Ishtahar*, p. 5.
- ²⁷ Malay Roychoudhury, *Ishtahar*, p. 8.
- ²⁸ Malay Roychoudhury, *Ishtahar*, p. 8.
- ²⁹ Subhash Ghosh, 'Khalasitolar 3no.,' in Ujjal Bandyopadhyay and Sabyasachi Sen ed. *Subhash Ghosh: Boisangraha I* (Kolkata: Gangchil, 2017), pp. 36-42.
- ³⁰ Basudeb Dasgupta, 'Randhansala,' in Sabyasachi Sen ed. *Hungry generation rachana samgraha* (Kolkata: Dey's Publishing, 2015), pp. 143-149.
- ³¹ Basudeb Dasgupta, 'Randhansala', p. 148.
- ³² Malay Roychoudhury, 'Amar generation er kabyadarshan', p. 21.
- ³³ Malay Roychoudhury, 'Amar generation er kabyadarshan', p. 30.
- ³⁴ Shaileshwar Ghosh, *Hungry generation aandolon*, p. 5.
- ³⁵ Buddhadeva Bose, *Damayanti* (Calcutta: Kabita Bhavan, 1943), p. 71.

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- ³⁶ Buddhadeva Bose, *Damayanti* (Calcutta: Kabita Bhavan, 1943), p. 71.
- ³⁷ Sudhindranath Dutta, 'Kabyer mukti', *Parichay* 1 (1931): 34.
- ³⁸ Shaileshwar Ghosh, 'Kabitar birudhey bidroho (i)', in *Protibad er sahitya* (Kolkata: Dhritarashtr prakashani, 1984), pp. 3-4.
- ³⁹ Malay Roychoudhury, *Malay Roychoudhurir kobita, 2004-1961* (Kolkata: Avishkar prakashani, 2006), pp. 193-207.
- ⁴⁰ 'Overused muscles are getting rusty frequently Equally true corpses of the wise and the ignorant are turning into slime being mixed with the soil At the problematic structure of the wound Every woman has been lurking with a conversion chart'
- ⁴¹ Subimal Basak, *Habijabi* (Calcutta: Alo Mitra, 1970), n.p.
- ⁴² 'What I will do now, I am not being able to understand properly I have come to the world with completely blank hands, true, trust me I was being called to be present inside the procession I was unable to match my voice with any other's'
- ⁴³ Malay Roychoudhury, *Malay Roychoudhurir kobita, 2004-1961* (Kolkata: Avishkar prakashani, 2006), p. 187.
- ⁴⁴ Malay Roychoudhury, 'Oshlilota', *Ishtahar sankalan* (Baruipur: Mahadiganta, 1985), p. 29.
- ⁴⁵ Shaileshwar Ghosh, *Shreshtho kabita* (Kolkata : Dey's Publishing, 2012), p. 40.
- ⁴⁶ Shaileshwar Ghosh, 'Bhasha bimochon', in Sabyasachi Sen ed. *Hungry generation rachana samgraha* (Kolkata: Dey's Publishing, 2015), p. 292.
- ⁴⁷ Friedrich Nietzsche, *Thus Spoke Zarathustra: A Book for Everyone and No One*. Trans. R. J. Hollingdale (London: Penguin Books, 1961), p. 85.
- ⁴⁸ Malay Roychoudhury, 'Amar generation er kabyadarshan,' in *Hungry kinbadanti-II* (Kolkata: Avishkar prakashani, 2013), pp. 21-31.
- ⁴⁹ Sekhar Bandyopadhyay, *Decolonization in South Asia: Meanings of freedom in post- independence West Bengal, 1947-52* (London: Routledge, 2009), p. 4.
- ⁵⁰ Shaileshwar Ghosh, 'Ghorar songe bhoutik kothabarta', in Sabyasachi Sen ed. *Hungry generation rachana samgraha* (Kolkata : Dey's Publishing, 2015), p. 35..
- ⁵¹ Shaileshwar Ghosh, *Shreshtho kabita* (Kolkata : Dey's Publishing, 2012)
- ⁵² Shaileshwar Ghosh, *Protibad er sahitya* (Kolkata: Dhritarashtr prakashani, 1984), p. 14.
- ⁵³ Malay Roychoudhury, *Ishtahar*, p. 5.
- ⁵⁴ Raymond Williams, *The Politics of Modernism*, p. 55.
- ⁵⁵ Shaileshwar Ghosh, 'Choritro-hinotar proyojon', *Protibad er sahitya* (Kolkata:

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- Dhritarashtr prakashani, 1984), p. 43.
- ⁵⁶ Wyndham Lewis, *Blast: Review of the Great English Vortex*. No. 1(London: John Lane, 1914), n.p.
- ⁵⁷ Shaileshwar Ghosh, *Protibader sahitya*, p. 3.
- ⁵⁸ Shaileshwar Ghosh, *Protibader sahitya*, p. 3.
- ⁵⁹ Sudhindranath Dutta, ‘Kabyer mukti’, *Parichay* 1 (1931): 30.
- ⁶⁰ Shaileshwar Ghosh, ‘Bhasha bimochon’, in Sabyasachi Sen ed. *Hungry generation rachana samgraha* (Kolkata: Dey’s Publishing, 2015), p. 303.
- ⁶¹ Malay Roychoudhury, *Ishtahar*, p. 53.
- ⁶² Partha Chatterjee, ‘The Political Culture of Calcutta’, p. 33.